

**BETWEEN TWO RIGHTS: BALANCING FREEDOM OF EXPRESSION WITH INDIVIDUAL'S
PRIVACY IN A DEMOCRATIC SOCIETY.**

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the intersection between the right to freedom of expression and the right to privacy. It analyzes how these rights conflict with each other, and at times, complement each other. This research adopts a doctrinal method, relying on legal essays and academic papers, on platforms such as ResearchGate and Academia.

Keywords: Democratic Society, Fundamental Human Rights, Freedom of Expression, Right to Privacy.

INTRODUCTION

The objectives of democracy is to "preserve and promote the dignity and fundamental rights of the individual; achieve social justice, strengthen the cohesion of society; enhance national tranquility; and create a climate that is favourable for international peace."¹⁸⁸ A territory where its people are able to freely express their thoughts and ideas and at the same time, able to limit its excesses, will serve as a democratic society. As a result, it is important that both rights are balanced so as to foster a society, where individuals can coexist within the borders the rights, that is; freedom of expression and right to privacy, provides.

THE RIGHT TO FREEDOM OF EXPRESSION

The right to freedom of expression is recognized and protected by both international laws and domestic laws. Article 19 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) provides that "everyone has the right to freedom of opinion and expression; this right includes freedom to hold opinions without interference and to seek, receive and impart information and ideas through any media and regardless of frontiers".¹⁸⁹ Article 19 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights gives a similar provision. However, it goes further to include the various forms through which a person can freely express themselves, either "orally, in writing, or in print, in the form of art or through any other action of his choice."¹⁹⁰

The African Charter of Human and People's Rights also provides that, "every individual shall have the right to receive information. Every individual shall have the right to express and disseminate his opinions within the law."¹⁹¹ In **Konate' v. Burkina Faso**¹⁹², the African Court of Human and Peoples' Rights delivered a landmark judgement on freedom of expression. Interpreting article 9, the judgement reversed the conviction of the journalist, Lohe' IssaKonate', who had been sentenced to prison for criminal defamation of a public official. He had accused the prosecutor of corruption. The African Court found that the conviction and sentence was disproportionate interference with the journalist's rights to freedom of expression guaranteed under Article 9 of the charter.

Freedom of expression constitutes one of the essential foundations of a democratic society and one of

188United Nations Human Rights Office of the High Commissioner, About Democracy and Human Rights <<https://www.ohchr.org/en/about-democracy-and-human-rights> accessed> 30 April 2025.

189 UDHR, (1948) art 19

190 ICCPR, (1966) art 19

191 ACHPR (1981) art 9.

192 (2014) AfCHPR App No 004/2013

the basic conditions for its progress.¹⁹³ Thus, as Nigeria transitioned from a military rule to a democratic state in 1999, this right was enshrined in her constitution by stating, "every person shall be entitled to freedom of expression, including freedom to hold opinions and to receive and impart ideas and information without interference."¹⁹⁴ The court also acknowledges in the case of **Inspector-General of Police v All Nigeria Peoples Party and others**,¹⁹⁵ that freedom of expression is the backbone of democracy.

The effect of this right, beyond being an instrument of democracy, is that it affords every person the entitlement to own, establish and operate any medium for the dissemination of information, ideas and opinions.¹⁹⁶ This has led to an influx of people creating and owning social media accounts or media houses, to the end that their thoughts are projected and their voices, heard. However, this right is not absolute and attached to it are corresponding responsibilities. The responsibility to not damage someone else's reputation while expressing oneself is one of the responsibilities associated with freedom of expression.¹⁹⁷ The issue, however, lies in the fact that, while many advocate for the enforcement of this right, they fail to observe the limitations it is subject to. Such assertion of the right to express one's thoughts throws open the space for individuals to commit online defamation and damage the reputation of others.¹⁹⁸

A large number of internet users no longer engage in sharing qualitative information that benefits the society rather they prefer to upload the private affairs of others. What was originally meant to be of great benefit to each individual and the society as a whole has only led to cases of online defamation, cyber bullying, and harassment, which is a danger to a person's reputation and right to privacy.

THE RIGHT TO PRIVACY

Some theorists consider the right to privacy to be a natural right. Natural Rights are those divine rights

193 Handyside v United Kingdom [1976] ECHR 5 (1976) 1 EHRR 737 at 751

194 CFRN (as amended), s. 39

195 (2007) AHRLR 179

196 CFRN (as amended), s. 39(2)

197 C. L. Eleziyenya, *Analysis of Freedom of Expression and Online Defamation in Nigeria* (November 2023)

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/375126753_ANALYSIS_OF_FREEDOM_OF_EXPRESSION_AND_ONLINE_DEFAMATION_IN_NIGERIA> accessed 25 April 2025.

198 I. Udofa, *The Right to Freedom of Expression and the Law of Defamation in Nigeria* (2011) International Journal of Advanced Legal Studies and Governance 2(1)

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/266341565_Right_to_Freedom_of_Expression_and_the_Law_of_Defamation_in_Nigeria> accessed 25 April 2025.

which are considered supreme to all other rights.¹⁹⁹ The right to privacy is also recognized by The Universal Declaration of Human Rights,²⁰⁰ making it a fundamental human right. It states that "no one shall be subjected to arbitrary or unlawful interference with his privacy, family, home or correspondence, nor to unlawful attacks on his honour and reputation. Everyone has the right to the protection of the law against such interference or attacks." In the case of *Hannover v. Germany*,²⁰¹ publications had been made by tabloid magazines of a series of photos of Princess Caroline of Monaco, taken without her knowledge. The European Court of Human Rights, was presented with a conflict between the freedom of the press and the right to protect private life, particularly of public figures. The Court however, held that the press reporting details about the applicant's personal life, while she was performing an official state function, did not fall under the watchdog role of the press and did not contribute to a debate of general interest.

As well, this right is enshrined in the Nigerian Constitution. It provides that: "the privacy of citizens, their homes, correspondence, telephone conversations and telegraphic communications is hereby guaranteed and protected."²⁰² The importance of this section is to protect events or activities that an individual seeks to keep private from the public. Thus, where an individual records the phone call of another and proceeds to share it online, without his consent, such individual will be said to have violated the right to privacy of another. It is argued that data protection is part of the right to privacy. Thus in Nigeria, the right to privacy is not only regulated by the Nigerian Constitution but by the National Data Protection Regulations, 2019 and the National Data Protection Act, 2023.

Various scholars admit to the difficulty associated with defining the word, "privacy". Even the Nigerian constitution, as well as, other international treaties are silent as to the definition of privacy. However, according to Black's Law Dictionary²⁰³, privacy means the "right to be let alone; the right of a person to be free from any unwarranted publicity; the right to live without any interference by the public in matters with which public is not necessarily concerned". Also, considering the elements of privacy could give more insight into what it entails. According to Solove,²⁰⁴ the components of privacy include:

1. Personal autonomy

199 Right to Privacy: It's Sanctity in India, Essay submitted for the Essay Writing Competition 2019, The Chamber of Tax Consultants, <<https://ctconline.org/wp-content/uploads/pdf/2019/seminar-presentation/essay/R-57.pdf>> accessed 25 April, 2025

200 UDHR (1948), art. 12

201 (2004) No 59320/00, ECtHR.

202CFRN (as amended), s37.

203 Black's Law Dictionary, 8th ed.

204 D J. Solove, *Understanding Privacy*, (Harvard University Press, 2008)

2. Limited access to the self
3. Confidentiality
4. The management of personal information
5. The right of individuality

These components further show that the right of privacy is personal to the individual and all that he owns. As such, consent is required from the individual before any information regarding him or his property is disseminated to a third party or the public.

THE INTERSECTION OF FREEDOM OF EXPRESSION AND RIGHT TO PRIVACY

There is apparent tension between the right that an individual has to express himself and the right of another to privacy. But, the right to freedom of expression and privacy are mutually reinforcing rights.²⁰⁵ They are sometimes complementary and most times, in collision. There are certain instances where the right to privacy strengthens the enforcement of the freedom of expression. One of such instances is where an individual stays freely expresses his thoughts and feelings, while remaining anonymous. Everyone should have a right to exercise his or her right to freedom of expression anonymously, which includes through anonymous speech, to read anonymously or to access information in online and physical environments anonymously."²⁰⁶ In such areas, the area of protection of privacy can be interpreted as a safeguard for robust and inhibited expression.²⁰⁷

Furthermore, a democratic state is built on the existence of both the right to freedom of expression and the right to privacy. For democracy, accountability and good governance to thrive, freedom of expression must be respected and protected.²⁰⁸ On the other hand, the aims which democracy seeks to achieve in a state, is defeated where the right to privacy is not enforced.

However, when there is a conflict between these rights, one of them is usually enforced over the other. This conflict could arise where one person's right to freely express himself may lead to an infringement on another's right to privacy. In such a scenario, the overemphasis on one of them is what leads to the

205 ARTICLE 19, *The Global Principles on Protection of Freedom of Expression and Privacy* (March 2017) <<https://www.article19.org/resources/the-global-principles-on-protection-of-freedom-of-expression-and-privacy/>> accessed 26 April 2025.

206 Ibid

207 Juan Manuel Ospina (ed), *Privacy and Freedom of Expression* (Global Freedom of Expression, 2023) <<https://globalfreedomofexpression.columbia.edu/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/Privacy-and-Freedom-of-Expression-4.pdf>> accessed 26 April 2025.

208 Ibid n2.

restriction of the other.

Furthermore, the balance between both rights is often drawn by the courts by considering the facts of each case that is brought before it. In considering the case of **Konate' v. Burkina Faso** and **Hannover v Germany**, while the facts of the cases may be prima facie similar, the different judgements delivered by the courts goes to show that the purpose of public interest, is a determining factor in deciding which right should prevail. In **Konate**, the court emphasized the importance of freedom of expression in promoting accountability in governance, which served the purpose of public interest. But, in **Hannover**, the court prioritized the right to privacy, noting that the publication of personal images was of no interest to the public and was thereby intrusive.

The above cases highlight that while both rights are fundamental, neither of them are absolute. As a result, a balance is struck between an individual's right to freedom of expression and right to privacy when the factor of public interest is used by the courts as a determining factor and weighed by both sides.

CONCLUSION

Abraham Lincoln's definition of democracy infers that the people are at the center of governance.²⁰⁹ Thus, a democratic society, is such that thrives on the recognition and protection of human rights, especially the right to freedom of expression and the right to privacy. These rights, though contrasting, are essential for the dignity and participation of individuals within such a society. Freedom of expression empowers citizens to engage in public affairs and influence governance by holding the elected authorities accountable. At the same time, the right to privacy shields those individuals from undue involvement in their personal affairs.

Overemphasis on either the freedom of expression or the right to privacy without regard for the other could lead to threats to personal and hinder transparency and accountability respectively. Therefore, it is crucial to strike a balance between these rights to ensure that one does not erode the other.

RECOMMENDATION

To ensure that there is harmonization between the enforcement of both rights, each arm of the government has a role to play. The Judiciary has the role to effectively apply and enforce either of these rights as it varies from circumstance to circumstance. In the case of *Olawayin v Attorney of Northern*

²⁰⁹ Abraham Lincoln, the 16th U.S. President defined democracy as the "Government of the people, by the people, for the people".

Nigeria,²¹⁰ it was held that the courts have been appointed sentinels to watch over the fundamental rights secured to the people of Nigeria by the Constitution and to guard against any infringement of those rights. Likewise, the legislature also has a role to play in crafting clear and precise laws that protects both rights and the penalty for infringement. Lastly, the executives, could carry out the public awareness needed to educate the public on the extent and limits associated with both rights. Where each arm of government work together in performing these roles, it will foster a society where freedom of expression is valued and the right to privacy, respected.

210 (1962) 1 All NIR 324